

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF MEASUREMENT METHODS IN ELECTRIC LIGHTING

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Introduction: This is a semiconductor device, and under the influence of radiation energy, it has an e.y.u.c. is formed. An electric current appears in the photocell circuit without external voltage. It depends on the radiation current falling on the photocell. That is, valve photocells are converters of radiant energy into electrical energy.

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Basic geometric concepts of photometry. (converter of radiation energy into electrical energy). Selenium photocells are the most common for light measurements, their spectral sensitivity corresponds very closely to the normalized function of the relative spectral effective irradiance of light.

1. A large steel plate (connected to the positive clamp) that serves as the base of the selenium photocell.
2. -A layer of selenium that is opaque to light rays.
3. Locking layer with unidirectional conductivity from selenium to gold.
4. Surface clear layer of gold or platinum (5nm).
5. A metal ring that is placed (coated) on gold (it is connected to the negative terminal of the photocell).
6. Galvanometer,

When exposed to light, electrons are released from the outer layer of selenium, and they can move through the blocking layer in only one direction (from the selenium to the gold layer). If a galvanometer is connected to the photocell clamps, then an electric current is generated in the circuit (the direction is shown in the figure).

Full correspondence of the photocurrent change in the plane of the photocell with respect to the illumination is maintained when it is short-circuited to the external circuit (Stoletov), that is, when its resistance is zero, when the resistance (galvanometer) is connected to the external circuit, the boom is broken, and this violation, the illumination in the plane of the photocell the larger, the higher, because the internal resistance of the selenium photocell decreases when the illumination is focused.

Figure 1. Selenium photovoltaic cell photocurrent depends on illumination at different resistances of the external circuit.

Advantages of selenium photocell

1. The maximum of the spectral sensitivity line of the selenium photocell is located close to the maximum of the relative spectral normalized line of light radiation.
 2. Not needing an external supply source;
 3. Correspondence between photocurrent and illumination;
 4. The integral sensitivity of the selenium photocell is in the range of 300 to 750 mka/lm and depends on the material of the outer electrode covering the selenium layer (great sensitivity to light)
- Disadvantage of SF:
- a) In the presence of an inertia phenomenon (the nominal current is set after 102 or 103 s after the start of lighting)
 - b) dependence of the photocurrent on the temperature of the external environment.

Photocell with external photoeffect (electrovacuum). This photocell is a two-electrode device housed in a spherical or cylindrical glass bulb. The anode of the photocell is made in the form of a ring made of thin nickel wire. A light-sensing layer attached to the inner surface of a glass tube or bent into the shape of a semi-cylindrical plate serves as the photocell cathode.

1. Glass flask;
2. Light-sensitive layer (cathode);
3. Photocell anode;
4. Connecting rods (rods);
5. F.E. Falcon;
6. Accumulator source;
7. Galvanometer.

The electric field between the cathode and the anode is created using a battery source.

Photons fall into the light-sensitive layer of F.E. and eject electrons from it, which fly towards the anode under the influence of the electric field between the anode and cathode, that is, F.E. is measured using a galvanometer according to the density of the light current falling on the cathode in the circuit. F.E. with external effect. vacuum (electronic) and gas-filled (ionic), the flask of which is filled with an inert gas after blowing air. Ionic F.E. electrons flying to the anode ionize gas atoms on their way, freeing new electrons. As a result, ionic F.E. photocurrent increases 6-10 times. Gas-filled F.E. in order to prevent arc discharge in the circuit, it is necessary to connect a large resistance that limits the anode voltage. Ionic F.E. advantages of Ionic (gas filled) F.E. electronic (vacuum) e. has a high integral sensitivity compared to . Ionic F.E. disadvantages of

Ionic F.E. Disadvantages (compared to vacuum F.E.):

- 1) Lack of proper correspondence between the photocurrent and the density of the light current falling on the cathode;

2) Low temperature resistance;

3) High shadow current;

Electric vacuum F.E. There is an integrated sensitivity lock layer F.E. low compared to (80-120 MKA/lm).

Measuring illumination Special photometric devices called luxmeters are used to measure illumination.

Luxmeter is a selenium F.E. and an indicator galvanometer (YU-16) is connected to its chain.

The scale of the galvanometer (level indicator), the spectral composition of an incandescent lamp of medium power (200-300 W) with a color temperature of $T=2854$ K and the spectral composition of radiation - according to the standard A source, directly graded in lux.

For measuring large values of illumination, the instrument is equipped with shunts and neutral filters, which are F.E. is put on (entered).

The YU-16 luxmeter does not have a correction filter, therefore, when measuring the illumination of a light source with a spectral composition different from the spectral composition of the standard A source, it is necessary to introduce correction coefficients (for LD lamps -0.9; L5- 1.1).

To eliminate this inconvenience, improved luxmeters have F.E. a special yellow-green light filter with low transmission in the violet and red parts of the spectrum is installed in front of it.

With the help of such luxmeters, the spectral composition of light can be measured without recalculating the illuminance from any source, because the line of spectral sensitivity of such luxmeters corresponds to the normalized line of relative spectral light efficiency.

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